

Representation Learning in Seismic Interpretation

“The unreasonable effectiveness of Seismic Autoencoders”

Steve Purves, Dimitris Oikonomou, Behzad Alaei, Eirik Larsen

AAPG ACE 2019

Lithostratigraphy & complex prograding channel systems

New Zealand: Taranaki Basin

CNN Based Fault Segmentation

Labelled crosslines evenly spaced across dataset

N

Quadrant: 7224
Structural Element:
Swaen Graben

Representation Learning

- Abstraction & generalisation
- Reusability
- Reliability
- Performance with fewer labels
- Using smaller networks

Exploring Seismic Representations

- ICA - independent component analysis
- Convolutional Autoencoders
- Wavelet Scattering Transforms
- Curvelets & *lets

Invariant Scattering Convolution
Networks [for image classification]

J. Bruna, S. Mallat

<https://arxiv.org/pdf/1203.1513.pdf>

Fundamental Representations

airplane

automobile

bird

cat

deer

dog

frog

horse

ship

truck

CIFAR-10 Dataset

<https://www.cs.toronto.edu/~kriz/cifar.html>

Learned Image Basis Set - Reconstruction ICA

Le, Karpenko, Ngiam, Ng; Stanford Univ.

Representations in Seismic

Learned Seismic Basis

Learned Vs Fixed Representations

RICA Basis Functions

Frequency Domain Coverage

Learned Vs Fixed Representations

Orientation, θ → Complex Wavelet Transform Kernels

Test Networks

Encoder Decoder Network

71,000 learnable parameters

Wavelet Network

52,000 learnable parameters

5,000 fixed wavelet parameters

Channels

Encoder Decoder

IOU 0.804 F1 0.890

Wavelet Network

IOU 0.813 F1 0.895

Channels - Encoder Decoder

Random Crossline outside of training set
(crossline is the training direction)

Channels - Wavelet Network

Random Crossline outside of training set
(crossline is the training direction)

Channels - Encoder Decoder

Random Inline
(network was not trained on inline sections)

Channels - Wavelet Network

Random Inline
(network was not trained on inline sections)

Faults

0 1500 3000 m

Encoder Decoder

Wavelet Network

Accuracy (Positive) 0.966

Accuracy (Positive) 0.958

Faults - Encoder Decoder

Faults - Wavelet Network

Encoder
Decoder
Network

timeslice

Wavelet
Network

Wavelet Network Low Level Features

network schematic

learned filters

learned filters
(close up)

network schematic

Learned 2d frequency domain coverage

Wavelet 2d frequency domain coverage

Conclusions

- Deterministic CNNs trained on interpretation tasks don't necessarily learn compact low level image representations - but perform well nevertheless
- Replacing learned low level features with wavelets scattering layers provides equivalent performance for ~25% fewer learnable parameters
- Further work required to test and measure any performance improvement in specific cases particularly 3D fault networks

Conclusions

- Examining CNN internal responses in a way relevant our domain can provide new insights into model performance and generalisation
- Developing further domain specific visualisations and metrics could provide new training and evaluation criteria for models. This work is ongoing.

Acknowledgements

- Work was carried out as part of the Petromaks 2 Research & Development programme - Supported by the Norwegian Research Council and our consortium partners (ConocoPhillips, Wintershall DEA, Spirit Petroleum, Lundin)
- Norwegian Petroleum Directorate for access to Barent Sea Dataset (NH0608)
- New Zealand Petroleum and Minerals (NZPM) for providing the Parihaka 3D Seismic Dataset

www.earthanalytics.ai

Steve Purves
steve.purves@earthanalytics.no
@stevejpurves

